

FLAX FILLED THERMOPLASTIC BIOCOMPOSITE DEVELOPMENT FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

S. Meatherall¹, F. Wheeler^{1*}, N. Granlund²

¹ Composites Innovation Centre, Winnipeg, Canada, ² Interfacial Solutions, River Falls, USA

* Corresponding author (fwheeler@compositesinnovation.ca)

Keywords: *thermoplastic, biocomposite, flax, automotive*

1 Introduction

Based on continuous interactions with large automotive and tractor companies and their tier one suppliers, the Composites Innovation Centre (CIC) has identified a drive in the automotive and agricultural vehicle industries to incorporate bio-based constituents and increase bio-content in their thermoplastic components to reduce weight, cost and plastic consumption. Relative to traditional composite reinforcements such as fibreglass, flax and bast fibres in general are nearly half the density of glass with comparable fibre bundle strength and are substantially less energy intensive to produce [1], the latter point being the greatest and most significant environmental benefit of flax over fibreglass.

It is recognized that one of the quickest and most practical avenues that biomaterials have made their way into the automotive market was through non-structural injection or compression moulded thermoplastic parts such as interior door panels, dashboard components or other plastic interior cabin parts. Daimler Chrysler has used natural fibres in interior components for years prior to developing an exterior underbody component with abaca fibres for its A-Class. Ford developed an interior storage bin for the 2010 Ford Flex using wheat straw filler in polypropylene. Although small interior components are low value/cost parts, the volumes associated with a single component in one vehicle model can equate to hundreds of tonnes of input biomass required.

Manitoba, Saskatchewan and Alberta grow approximately 1.2 to 1.7 million acres of linseed flax annually which equates to approximately 40% of the world's oil seed flax production [2], with significant production also coming from China, India and the United States. This equates to approximately 240 to 340 thousand tonnes of flax fibre produced annually.

SWM, the world's largest flax processor, with their North America operations located in Carman Manitoba processes between 100 and 150 thousand tonnes of flax straw annually. This equates to approximately 80 to 120 thousand tonnes of flax shive (inner woody core) which is considered a by-product of their processing and has traditionally brought little to no income in applications for cattle bedding or as a combustible biomass. However, with the recent implementation of their flax shive cleaning plant, SWM can now produce clean and consistent screen sizes of shive which will be investigated in this project as a suitable filler in thermoplastic automotive components.

Before such materials can be presented to the manufacturers and their suppliers for adoption into their respective vehicles substantial precursor development activities are required. Such development activities include optimization of material formulas and blends, mechanical and physical property benchmarking, environmental durability evaluations, processing/manufacturing studies and material cost analysis.

The wood plastic composite (WPC), or wood polymer composite, industry is already fairly well established, and as such the knowledge gained in the WPC industry serves a solid basis for comparing the viability of flax filled composites both from a technical and economic stand point.

This paper encapsulates a component of the CIC's ongoing engineering development and optimization project to evaluate and demonstrate flax shive as a low density, inexpensive filler with some reinforcing value in thermoplastic polymers for automotive injection and compression moulded applications.

2 Approach and Scope

As mentioned in the introduction, flax shive can be obtained in commercial quantities with consistent screen sizes and a high quality of cleanliness. Due to being a by-product of large flax fibre processing operations, there is an abundance of shive available. Flax shive has a higher aspect ratio than flax flour, potentially providing some reinforcing value to the composite. Although flax shive as a filler for composites was investigated for the aforementioned reasons, it was desirable to process short flax fibre composites using the same compounding and composite processes as a comparison. Flax fibre, even when short, has a significantly higher aspect ratio and can theoretically compete with glass fibre properties on a by weight basis [3] [4]; however, fibres are more prone to agglomeration and difficulties in feeding REF [5]; as compared to the shive used.

Due to the nature of manufacturing (injection moulding, extrusion, etc.) of thermoplastic composites the fibre needs to be reduced to short fibre lengths in the 3 to 6mm range. Even at these fibre lengths, short fibre was expected to agglomerate or show difficulties with feeding and dispersion. Shive was expected to flow better than short fibre in the compounding process; however, due to the bulkiness of the shive particles the surface finish of the end biocomposite may be compromised as compared to biocomposites using flour or short fibre based formulations.

The project includes preliminary formulating and compounding trials in order to select the better of the flax shive or short cut fibre for manufacturability and also as a reinforcement/filler in each of the polymers.

Versatile, a division of Buhler Industries Inc., the only Canadian manufacturer of agricultural tractors, located in Winnipeg Manitoba, has provided the project team with a direct application to target with the flax based thermoplastic development. The material currently in their production line is a particular grade of acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS). ABS properties provided for targeting are displayed in Fig. 1.

This project also builds on a prior flax filled thermoplastic study carried out by the Composites Innovation Centre (CIC) and Interfacial Solutions

(IFS) that evaluated flax flour filled composites against their respective neat polymer for polypropylene (PP), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), and polylactic acid (PLA) each at three (3) different flax flour loadings. Test results for this study are displayed in Fig. 2. The flax component used was SWM's FlaxFlour™ product, Fig. 3.

Based on the results seen in Fig. 2, the impact properties of the PP and PLA see slight increases and decreases depending on the flax flour loading level, but remain relatively insignificant, likely due to the polymers inherently low impact strength. However, the HDPE's impact strength is greatly reduced with the addition of flax flour. The flexural strength of PP and PLA decreases with an increase in flax loading levels, whereas HDPE sees a slight increase in flexural strength at lower flax loading levels. In all cases the flexural modulus improves with increasing flax loading levels up to the maximum tested loading level of 45% flax flour.

With ABS being the application's benchmark material for the flax-based thermoplastic biocomposite development, much of the focus has turned to identifying the appropriate impact modifiers for the material formulations. This is discussed in greater detail in section 3.3 below. A flax filled ABS formulation has been included the project, and although PP was investigated in the prior flax flour filled thermoplastic evaluation, its properties are unlikely to meet the specification put forth by Versatile, and as such it was not included in the scope of this project. PLA's impact properties were significantly lower than the targets; however its flexural modulus was within range. It was selected for further analysis due to being a potentially viable bio-based plastic option.

The scope of the project encompasses benchmarking activities, formulation and compounding trials, optimization of properties using additives and modifiers, testing, followed by a cost analysis and field trials. The benchmarking process will evaluate two (2) untreated flax filled synthetic systems and one (1) flax filled bio-based thermoplastic system. The formulating and compounding trials will include both synthetic and bio-based polymers with either flax shive or short flax fibre at viable loading levels, with additives and modifiers targeting specific material property improvements. A comprehensive mechanical and physical test program will be conducted to support down-selecting prior to

performing interior automotive specific evaluations including material off-gassing (fogging), exposure (xenon-arc) and flammability. Finally, the merit and practicality of the developed material will be evaluated through a cost analysis and the implementation, field trials and evaluation of the material in a tractor part application.

The scope of this paper encompasses only the benchmarking activities, formulation and compounding trials, optimization of properties using additives and modifiers, and the mechanical and physical test program.

3 Materials

The materials and associated modifiers selected for the development of flax-based thermoplastic formulations are introduced and discussed in this section.

3.1 Base Polymers

With ABS being the application's benchmark material for the biocomposite development, a flax filled ABS formulation was included in this project. ABS is derived from acrylonitrile, butadiene, and styrene. Acrylonitrile is a synthetic monomer produced from propylene and ammonia; butadiene is a petroleum hydrocarbon; styrene monomer is made by dehydrogenation of ethyl benzene — a hydrocarbon obtained in the reaction of ethylene and benzene. ABS combines the strength and rigidity of acrylonitrile and styrene polymers with the toughness of polybutadiene rubber. ABS has excellent impact resistance, moderate strength, and good cosmetic appearance due to its styrene content. However, it is somewhat more expensive than HDPE.

HDPE is a petroleum based polymer known for its flexibility, strength to density ratio, chemical and impact resistance, and low cost. HDPE has a higher specific strength than low-density polyethylene because of stronger intermolecular forces in the polymer and tensile strength, due to little branching. HDPE is a conventional WPC base resin, and as such was included in the project as a viable candidate for flax based HDPE formulations.

Another objective with this project is to investigate a bio-based thermoplastic system for a flax-based composite using PLA. PLA is a polyester derived

from renewable resources, such as corn starch, tapioca (cassava) roots, or sugarcane. Note that the flax flour filled thermoplastic evaluation shows PLA out-performing PP on impact strength, flexural strength, and flexural modulus, Fig. 2.

3.2 Flax Fibre Production & Processing

Bast fibre crops such as linseed flax are annually renewable crops commonly grown in North America. Traditionally, flax grown in North America has been cultivated for its oil seeds for use in nutritional foods, animal feed, cosmetics and lubricants. After the crops are harvested for their seeds, a significant amount of straw biomass is left behind (~2.5 - 10 tonnes/hectare), which until recently was baled and stored by the farmer, burnt, or tilled back into the earth. The re-emergence of bast fibres for industrial applications not only creates a practical use for these materials, but also generates a secondary revenue stream for the crop, significantly benefiting rural communities. Additionally, flax is a robust crop requiring minimal herbicides, pesticides and irrigation.

Decortication is the process of mechanically separating the inner woody core (shive in flax) from the outer fibre layer. Traditional linseed flax straw contains approximately 20% fibre by weight. Decortication is most commonly performed by hammermilling or rollermilling. Hammermilling consists of single or multiple concurrent drums rotating with "hammers" or "plates" projecting transversely from the drum surface that "beat" the straw within the enclosed housing until the separated shive and fibre particles can pass freely through the mesh screens that enclose the hammermill. Due to the density differences between the core and fibre, pneumatic separation aids this separation process. Roller mills consist of long cylindrical corrugated rollers that are angled in such orientations as to break open the straw stalks while producing minimal damage to the fibre. Core and fibre separation occurs as a result of continuous agitation over slotted screens throughout the milling process. Subsequent steps common to both decortication processes include a method of bale opening (guillotine cutters, bale breaking or bale unrolling), additional fibre and shive separation (step cleaners, straw walkers, duvex), dust extraction, fibre opening, core bagging and fibre baling. The major benefit of hammermilling is the high throughput capability (~5 – 15 tonnes/hr straw input), but

include disadvantages such as lack of fibre length control, the potential to only create small to medium size fibres (1 – 10cm), damaged fibre and fibre-core entanglement. Rollermilling gives much greater length control, has the ability to produce very long fibre (30 – 60cm) and will better preserve the integrity of the fibres. However, rollermilling inherently has a much smaller throughput capacity relative to hammermilling (~1 – 3 tonnes/hr straw input).

As a large volume flax processor, SWM uses the hammermilling decortication technique. SWM's FlaxStalk™ product line offers a range of fibre, shive, and flour blends. The FlaxFill™ product is a premium flax shive fraction intended for use as a filler or extender for composite applications, and as such was used as the flax shive component in this study, Fig. 4.

SWM's Flax80Blend™ is a blend targeting 80% flax fibre content, Fig. 5. The Flax80Blend™ was processed in a RETSCH SM300 Cutting Mill. Fibres of 10 – 60mm in length were fed into the SM300 with the desire to achieve a processed fibre length of 6mm (1/4"). For fibrous material processing purposes the SM300 is configured with a universal hopper, parallel section rotor, 4mm sieve, and cyclone collection system. All samples were processed at 1500rpm. An initial processing run was carried out without the cyclone collection system in place and resulted in significant material build up within the grinding chamber, Fig. 6 and Fig 7.

3.3 Impact modification

As previously described and detailed in Fig 2, the impact properties of the PLA were not substantially impacted with the flax flour loading level, likely due to the polymers inherently low impact strength. The HDPE's impact strength; however, was reduced to only 20% of its original value with the addition of only 25% flax flour. In all cases the flexural modulus improves with increasing flax loading levels up to the maximum tested loading level of 45% flax flour. Higher loading levels were not evaluated as flexural modulus has a tendency to increase until the point where the material becomes too weak from lack of resin (often above 65% flour).

The target values in Fig. 1 show an impact requirement significantly higher than that achieved

with any of the PLA or HDPE and flax flour blends while the flexural modulus meets or exceeds the requirement. A balance between flax loading levels, impact strength and flexural modulus is required to meet the target objectives, with a special focus on improving the impact properties while maintaining an appreciable biocontent. To achieve this, two types of impact modifier methods were chosen: use impact modifiers that are known to work in cellulose filled resin systems and in resin systems that are typically not filled, use modifiers that are known to increase the impact of the resin itself.

In previous work done by IFS with WPC's using HDPE as the base resin it has been observed that a 50% wood filled composite can achieve a 200% increase in impact properties using 2% maleic anhydride grafted HDPE (MAPE). Given that flax is also a cellulose based material, this would be a top candidate for flax/high density composites.

Other impact modifiers considered for the flax/HDPE composites are maleic anhydride grafted EPDM (MA-EPDM) and an ethylene octene-octene copolymer. MA-EPDM is being considered due to the fact that EPDM alone can be used as an impact modifier for polyolefins. Therefore, it was hypothesized that the use of a maleic anhydride functionalized EPDM would be a viable choice for cellulose filled HDPE. The ethylene-octene copolymer was considered because like EPDM, it's a very rubbery polymer that can impart elastomeric qualities to an HDPE composite system. Unlike EPDM it has much higher ethylene content and therefore should be more miscible in HDPE.

Impact modifiers for PLA composites have not really been established; however, it is known that the use of Biostrength 150 from Arkema Inc. can improve impact dramatically when used at 10% by weight [6] in the neat resin.

Impact modification for ABS are typically not needed for most applications that ABS is used for; however, the addition of fillers to this resin often have detrimental effects on its physical properties. To help ABS retain its impact properties the choice of an Elvaloy acrylate copolymer was made based off of the literature available from DuPont on filled ABS systems. According to their website the use of 5-10% Elvaloy acrylate copolymer can increase the toughness of a filled system by 300% [7].

4 Composite Manufacturing

In order for natural fibre reinforcements to succeed in the composite industry they must be able to be processed by current composite fabricating methods with as little variation or disruption to the manufacturing processes then what is experienced when using traditional synthetic materials.

Extrusion and injection moulding are composite manufacturing processes that often utilize short fibres or wood flour (or potentially ground flax or hemp core) as the reinforcement or filler in the injection/extrusion compound.

Plastic products of uniform cross-section can be readily produced by the extrusion process. Thermoplastic pellets are fed through a hopper into the barrel of a screw extruder where a rotating screw (or often two) propels the material through a heating section where the thermoplastic compound is homogenized, compressed and then forced through a heated die onto a conveyor where the part is cooled by either air or water [8]. Common products produced by extrusion include decking, fencing, trim and moulding, window frames, doors, roofing and numerous other products of constant cross-section. However, injection moulding is the most widely used process for high-volume production of thermoplastic parts [8].

4.1 Compounding and testing procedures for the creation of flax composites.

For this study the flax shive was dried to less than 1% moisture before compounding in various resin systems.

The creation of flax composites was achieved by compounding on a twin screw extruder. The extruder used for the preparation of flax composites created for this study was a Lab Tech 26mm co-rotating parallel twin screw extruder with a 40:1 L:D fitted with a 4 strand die. The screw design used for such compounding was as follows: 338cm of conveying elements, 84.5mm of kneading elements, 109mm of conveying elements, 32mm of kneading elements, 54mm of conveying, 54mm of kneading followed by conveying elements until the end of the screw design. Such a screw design is not required for WPC compounding but a screw with three separate short kneading sections (60-90mm) amongst

conveying is typically employed. The extruder itself is manufactured by Lab Tech engineering. Compounding was typically done at 200 rpm with an extrusion rate of 4.5-6.8kg/hr. Extrusion temperatures for all 9 zones and the die are 180 °C. The resulting strands were conveyed on an 8' (2.4m) conveyor belt with fans cooling the strands before being pelletized to a length of 0.64 cm.

In order to test physical properties samples were injection moulded into standard ASTM shapes for tensile, flexural and impact property testing. Such moulding was done on an Engel 90 ton injection moulder equipped with a standard moulding screw, tip and sprue. For the composites that were moulded in this study an injection boost pressure of 10,300kPa (1500psi) was used. The hold pressure profile consisted of a straight 3,500kPa (500psi) in all zones with a hold time of 3 seconds. Screw speed was set at 55% of total screw rotation speed along with a backpressure of 140kPa (20psi) to minimize the shear energy that the rotation of the screw put in the composites. Cool time was 12sec in a mould heated to 32 °C. Barrel temperatures were: 154 °C (zone 3), 171 °C (zone 2), 171 °C (zone 3) and 188 °C at the nozzle. Resulting parts were tested using ASTM method D638 for tensile properties, D790 for flexural properties and D256 for izod impact properties.

5 Test Program

As mentioned above, a previous study of flax flour filled thermoplastics results were taken into account and therefore have shaped the test program developed for this study.

ABS, HDPE, and PLA were compounded with the appropriate flax filler (shive or short fibre) at a flax loading level of 25%. The study was comprised of a total of twelve formulations. A formulation matrix by weight percentage of the three (3) resin systems and their respective modifiers is displayed in Fig. 8.

Flexural, tensile, impact, melt flow index, specific gravity and moisture resistance were determined for each formulation and benchmarked against their respective base resin systems.

At the time of submission, material compounding and testing is underway. Results will be shared at the conference.

The resulting experiments will provide a detailed picture of flax composite performance for comparison to conventional WPC formulations. The base resin systems will also be benchmarked.

Tables

ABS 750			
Properties	Units	Typical Values	ASTM Standard
Specific Gravity	g/cc	1.04	D-792
Melt Index	g/10min	1.7	D-1238
Gloss, 60°	%	90	D-523
Tensile Strength	MPa	35	D-638
Flexural Modulus	MPa	1,862	D-790
Impact Strength, Notched Izod	J/m		D-256
	73°F	336.42	
	-40°F	117.48	

Fig. 1. Material Properties of ABS.

	SI Units					Imperial Units				
	Izod impact (J/m)	Flexural Modulus (MPa)		Flexural Strength (MPa)		Izod impact (ft-lb/in)	Flexural Modulus (psi)		Flexural Strength (psi)	
	Notched	Average	S.D.	Average	S.D.	Notched	Average	S.D.	Average	S.D.
100% PP	18.2	1744	11	56	0.2	0.34	253000	1640	8070	31
75% PP, 25% Flax	19.4	1993	28	48	0.4	0.36	289000	4090	6920	63
70% PP, 30% Flax	22.1	1958	20	47	0.4	0.42	284000	2960	6770	59
55% PP, 45% Flax	17.4	2330	30	45	0.9	0.33	338000	4380	6520	131
100% HDPE	468.9	820	23	25.30	0.11	8.79	119000	3390	3670	16
75% HDPE, 25% Flax	89.1	1393	28	32.20	0.19	1.67	202000	4040	4670	28
70% HDPE, 30% Flax	77.9	1524	41	32.89	0.45	1.46	221000	5880	4770	65
55% HDPE, 45% Flax	49.1	1875	83	28.47	1.37	0.92	272000	12100	4130	198
100% PLA	25.7	3096	28	97.21	1.0	0.48	449000	4110	14100	145
75% PLA, 25% Flax	26.8	3778	30	79.98	0.8	0.50	548000	4280	11600	110
70% PLA, 30% Flax	24.5	3833	58	79.29	0.8	0.46	556000	8350	11500	112
55% PLA, 45% Flax	21.0	4516	104	67.29	0.6	0.39	655000	15100	9760	88.7

Fig. 2. Flax flour filled thermoplastic evaluation,

**FLAX FILLED THERMOPLASTIC BIOCOMPOSITE DEVELOPMENT
FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS**

Sample	HDPE	MA-HDPE	MA-EPDM	Engage 8003	PLA	BioStrength 150	ABS	Elvaloy AC	Flax	Sum of Percentages
1	75								25	100
2	73	2							25	100
3	71	4							25	100
4	73		2						25	100
5	71		4						25	100
6	70			5					25	100
7	65			10					25	100
8					75				25	100
9					65	10			25	100
10							75		25	100
11							70	5	25	100
12							65	10	25	100

Fig. 8. Material Formulation Matrix.by % Weight.

Figures

Fig. 3. SWM's FlaxFlour™

Fig. 5. SWM's Flax80Blend™ – Flax Fibre.

Fig. 4. SWM's FlaxFill™ – Flax Shive.

Fig. 6. Remaining Flax Fibre in RETSCH SM300 Grinding Chamber without use of Cyclone Collection System.

Fig. 7. Remaining Flax Fibre in RETSCH SM300 Grinding Chamber with use of Cyclone Collection System.

<http://www.gov.mb.ca/trade/globaltrade/agrifood/commodity/flax.html>. [Accessed 14 June 2013].

- [3] R. M. Rowell, "Natural fibres: types and properties," in *Properties and performance of natural-fibre composites*, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2008, pp. 3-66.
- [4] F. T. Wallenberger and P. A. Bingham, *Fiberglass and Glass Technology: Energy-Friendly Compositions and Applications*, Springer, 2009, p. 211.
- [5] M. Sain and S. Panthapulakkal, "Green fibre thermoplastic composites," in *Green composites*, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2004, pp. 181-206.
- [6] Natureworks LLC, "Ingeo extrusion blow molding guide," Natureworkslc.com, 23 July 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.natureworkslc.com/>. [Accessed 14 June 2013].
- [7] Dupont, "ABS polymer modifiers page," Dupont.com, 23 July 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www2.dupont.com/home/en-us/index.html>. [Accessed 14 June 2013].
- [8] J. T. Black and R. A. Kohser, "Fabrication of Plastics, Ceramics, and Composites," in *DeGarmo's Materials and Processes in Manufacturing*, 10th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc, 2008, pp. 334-362.

References

- [1] M. S. Huda and L. T. Drzal, "Processing of natural-fiber composites for the automotive sector," in *Properties and performance of natural-fibre composites*, Woodhead Publishing Limited, 2008, pp. 231-233.
- [2] Government of Manitoba, "Commodities: Grains and Oilseeds, Flax," Government of Manitoba, [Online]. Available: